

CONSISTENCY AS A PEDAGOGICAL PHENOMENON IN THE CONTINUING EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Consistency issues are studied in many works on the science of pedagogy. Depending on the approach to its analysis, consistency is defined as a pedagogical or didactic principle. The article examines the issues of determining the state of the problem of consistency in the theory of pedagogy and clarifying the essence of consistency as a pedagogical phenomenon.*

Keywords: *consistency, pedagogy, pedagogical principle, didactic principle, essence of consistency, higher education, educational system.*

When transitioning to continuous education, the task of acquiring independent knowledge and forming practical activity skills of learners becomes relevant. Not only acquiring knowledge, but mastering the methods of acquiring it, developing the knowledge-acquiring powers and creative potential of a person becomes the main goal of the educational process.

The main tasks of the continuous pedagogical education system development are as follows[14]:

1. Updating the content and goals of continuous pedagogical education, taking into account the social and economic requirements for the professional competence of educational specialists.
2. Modernization of forms, methods, and technologies of the educational process based on problem-based research, active, collective learning strategy.
3. Improving the training of highly qualified scientific staff, taking into account the current problems of modern psychological-pedagogical sciences, educational practice, principles of continuity and consistency.
4. Transition to the cluster model of development aimed at increasing the quality of pedagogical education based on the integration of educational opportunities of subjects of psychological and pedagogical science and effective educational practice.
5. Improving the means of the continuous pedagogical education system in the conditions of the information system and increasing the position of the pedagogical profession[14].

No matter how important consistency is, it should be noted that it cannot be absolute in the organization of the educational system. But it is important to ensure consistency in educational content.

A number of studies have been conducted on coherence, cross-disciplinary and intra-disciplinary communication in science teaching. Consistency is different in different subjects, for example, the consistency of knowledge in the process of learning the Uzbek language is as follows:

- in the sequential study of language events;
- in studying linguistic material based on the school program;
- is manifested in the study of the subject [1].

Sh.Yoldosheva studied the consistency of teaching compound nouns in mother tongue

classes [8].

M.Djuraev [6] researched methods of teaching probabilistic-statistical ideas and concepts based on the principle of consistency in the theory course of a higher educational institution. The researcher explains that the principle of consistency in teaching physics is similar to the principle of compatibility. "Because according to this principle, from any newly created theory, when certain conditions are met, the results of the previous theory confirmed by experience should follow" [67].

M.E.Nasirova conducted research on ensuring consistency in mathematics teaching at the School and Pedagogical Institute [15].

After consistency in education was recognized as belonging to the principles of didactics, its importance increased significantly. Sh.I.Ganelin[4] criticized the understanding of consistency in pedagogy as the main part of the principle of systematicity and sequence of teaching, because in this view, the problem of consistency is, on the one hand, only the knowledge and skills provided in programs, training manuals and textbooks, methodological manuals and is limited by the interaction of skills and, on the other hand, by the teacher's performance system. Such an approach, in his opinion, is one-sided, because "an important aspect of the problem of coherence is the question of the internal interrelationships of the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in the minds of students, the question of the effectiveness of the teacher's work in terms of the quality of mastery of the educational material taught to them by the students. , it is a matter of developing the whole personality of the student" [44]. According to Sh.I.Ganelin, "consistency is building on what has been learned in such a way as to apply and further develop the knowledge, skills and abilities that students already have in such a way that various connections are made in the minds of students, the main ideas of the course are revealed, old and new knowledge interact, resulting in a thorough and a system of deep knowledge is formed" [4, p. 126].

Thus, from the pedagogical point of view, when describing the principle of consistency in teaching, researchers note the following main directions: relying on the learned educational material; development of existing knowledge, skills and abilities; establishing various contacts; repetition of educational material at a higher level, that is, the interaction of old and new knowledge, skills and abilities; reveal the main ideas of the course; focus on moving from one step to the next in learning the learning material. Analyzing the diversity of consistency in higher education shows the universality of this category. Consistency is observed between the main components of the entire educational system and its relations with society, as well as in the simple act of learning. However, it is impossible to reveal the scientific content of this universal pedagogical concept by listing the manifestations of consistency. This issue cannot be resolved by expressing definitions of consistency that apply to particular pedagogical phenomena[16].

In addition, studies mainly focused on problems of consistency between educational institutions, compatibility of training programs, forms of organization of educational activities, matching the age-specific capabilities of students, changing the method of relations between students and teachers, universities, schools and universities, and other issues. At the same time, the importance of such cooperation is emphasized in order to establish complete consistency in the education of schoolchildren and university students.

Describing consistency as a methodological principle, E.A.Baller emphasizes the idea that "consistency is a connection between different stages or stages of development, the essence

of which is to preserve one or other elements of the whole or some aspects of its structure in changing the whole as a system" [3, p. 15 .].

According to A.A.Mukashev, "the understanding of consistency in the most general way is that in the movement from simple to complex, the process of transferring certain material and spiritual values takes place, the conflict of maintaining the achieved level of development by changing it is resolved" [13].

Consistency in education is the modern development of students' knowledge system in the process of teaching them the basics of science. It is carried out in each lesson by connecting new educational material with recent and previously acquired knowledge about similar phenomena of reality. Consistency in the transition from lesson to lesson, that is, in the system of lessons, in the transition from one academic year to another, from one academic subject to another close to it, etc. is carried out and shows its general pedagogical character.

In the following years, active research was conducted on the aspect of consistency in teaching, related to the problems of interdisciplinary communication, and the search for the didactic basis of the connection between teaching and student work. P.R. to develop these issues. Atutov [2] and others contributed greatly. While working out the issues of improving the educational process in higher education, some pedagogues came to the conclusion that the solution to a number of problems of higher education pedagogy lies at the intersection of secondary, vocational and higher schools.

In many ways, the leading concept of pedagogy - the idea of developmental and problem-based teaching helped to achieve consistency in teaching and acceleration of students' thinking at all levels of the public education system [9, 10, 11, 12].

M.I.Makhmutov [9, 10, 11, 12] and V.S. Bezrukovalar[12] developed a system of teaching principles specific to vocational education institutions, which ensures the interdependence of general and vocational education. These are the principles of career orientation, inter-disciplinary inter-cycle relations, study and work motivation, consistency, unity of education and training. Their implementation, according to the author's idea, adds a sufficiently clear goal orientation to the structure of the teaching content and the structure of the process and ensures the continuous development of the future specialist. In the process of implementation of education, these principles combine, enter into a mutual relationship, merge with each other and cause each other.

According to the historical-theoretical analysis of the problem and the study of the current situation, the concept of consistency itself is often a condition, requirement, factor, law, principle, rule, etc. has a multi-sense interpretation as In fact, consistency is a very important category of pedagogy that has an independent status. In pedagogy, there is still no single approach to defining this concept. E.A. Baller[3] describes the unsatisfactory state of research of consistency in pedagogy and writes: "Unfortunately, in general, all these issues, both theoretically and historically, are not yet researched on the scale required by their real importance and the practical needs of the development of society" [3].

S.M.Godnik [5] also emphasizes the multifacetedness and multifactorial nature of consistency in teaching. While researching the high and middle school consistency process, S.M.Godnik [5] showed the most important features of the problem of consistency of teaching in different educational institutions:

Table 1

The most important features of the problem of teaching consistency in the conditions of different educational institutions

№	Characteristic	Content
1	<i>Different properties</i>	Consistency is implemented at different pedagogical "stages".
2	<i>Multi-complexity</i>	Each component of the education and training system is considered and studied from the ideological, spiritual, professional activity, aesthetic and other aspects of education.
3	<i>Versatility</i>	Socio-economic, psychological, didactic, pedagogical and other aspects of consistency are studied
4	<i>Multifactoriality</i>	The nature of general educational preparation, the level of vocational orientation of students, etc. is studied

According to M.I.Makhmutov [9, 10, 11, 12] and V.S.Bezrukova [12], the principle of teaching consistency is manifested in:

- further development of the total positive aspects formed in the previous stages of education in students and pupils;
- ensuring the systematicity of knowledge and further developing the content, forms and methods of effective professional and technical education;
- progressive use of the content, methods and forms of education that help in the development of a person.

Therefore, the principle of consistency in teaching closely interacts with other principles and focuses on playing its positive role in the overall approach to the organization and management of the educational process in the entire educational system and in the educational activities of students in higher education. Organization of education in accordance with this principle allows for more precise demarcation of the content and functions of its separate stages, leads to the elimination of repetitions, ensures coordination of pedagogical actions, reduces the wrong use of time, provides students with deeper and more thorough knowledge related to professional activity.

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